

MORAL PROBLEMS IN CONTEMPORARY PHYSICAL CULTURE AND HEALTH EDUCATION

PROBLEMY MORALNE WE WSPÓŁCZESNEJ KULTURZE FIZYCZNEJ A EDUKACJA ZDROWOTNA

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Summary

The stars of the sport create very strong and lasting attitudes towards sport by being successful, but also give a personal example of being very public people with a given image. This indicates a great impact on the behavior of supporters and social groups identifying with the athletes. Creating attitudes unintentionally and the private life of a sports star that is far from a healthy lifestyle causes a negative impact on society but positive patterns and joining health-oriented campaigns brings high social and cultural benefits. In the modern world, we are increasingly reaching for products that complement our daily diet. The problem concerns the use of supplements and boosters that help faster fat burning and building muscle mass. Also, serious problem is that young people who start their sports journey, wanting to impress others, decide to consume substances of different origin. They reach for illegal supplements, which often ends in tragedy. Despite very widespread actions that inform about the harmful effects of using these dangerous drugs, young people and sometimes athletes reach for them. People who take these substances try to escape problems in this way. They don't even realize they're addicted. The effects can be tragic and many young athletes have lost their careers through drugs and alcohol. Physical education plays the role of a message, which is focused on creating the right set of attitudes and attitudes, the transmission of messages associated with it, as well as hardening for environmental stimuli and acquiring skills and abilities that together determine the behavior of a person in relation to his physical (bodily) characters. Almost all of us have to deal with physical culture in our lives – playing sports, actively relaxing or attending physical education classes. It is identified with attention to physical fitness and health, striving for the correct body posture, and proper psychophysical development. Physical culture is strongly associated with morality because it is visible in all forms of physical culture. Nowadays, health education, which is implemented at individual educational stages, plays a big role in school education. Thanks to this, already at school we can develop the habit of caring systematically for our own health and decide on active participation in physical culture. Physical fitness was already of great importance to primitive people, because they had to be strong, fit, healthy, resistant to diseases and a changing climate. Many scholars were interested in sport and physical culture. The beginnings of physical education in Europe should be traced to ancient Greece.

Keywords: professional sport, health education, physical culture, morality.

Gwiazdy sportu tworzą bardzo silny i trwały stosunek do sportu, odnosząc sukcesy, ale także dają osobisty przykład bycia bardzo publicznymi ludźmi o danym wizerunku. Wskazuje to na duży wpływ na zachowanie kibiców i grup społecznych identyfikujących się ze sportowcami. Niezamierzone kreowanie postaw, a życie prywatne gwiazdy sportu dalekiej od zdrowego stylu życia, wywiera negatywny wpływ na społeczeństwo, ale pozytywne wzorce i przyłączanie się do kampanii prozdrowotnych przynosi duże korzyści społeczne i kulturowe.

Słowa kluczowe: sport zawodowy, edukacja zdrowotna, kultura fizyczna, moralność.

Зірки спорту створюють дуже сильне та довготривале ставлення до спорту, домагаючись успіху, але також дають особистий приклад бути дуже публічними людьми із заданим іміджем. Це свідчить про великий вплив на поведінку прихильників та соціальних груп, що ототожнюють спортсменів. Ненавмисне створення ставлення та особисте життя спортивної зірки, що веде далеко не здоровий спосіб життя, спричиняє негативний вплив на суспільство, але позитивні зразки та приєднання до кампаній, орієнтованих на здоров'я, приносять високу соціальну та культурну користь. Проблема стосується використання добавок та бустерів, які допомагають швидше спалювати жир та нарощувати м'язову масу. Також серйозною проблемою є те, що молоді люди, які починають свій спортивний шлях, бажаючи вразити інших, вирішують споживати речовини різного походження. Вони вживають незаконні добавки, які часто закінчуються трагедією. Незважаючи на дуже поширені дії, які інформують про шкідливий вплив вживання цих небезпечних наркотиків, молодь та іноді спортсмени до них тягнуться. Люди, які приймають ці речовини, намагаються таким чином уникнути проблем. Вони навіть не розуміють, що залежні. Наслідки можуть бути трагічними, і багато молодих спортсменів втратили свою кар'єру через наркотики та алкоголь. Фізичне виховання відіграє роль повідомлення, яке орієнтоване на створення пра-

вильного набору поглядів та установок, передачу пов'язаних з ним повідомлень, а також загартовування екологічних стимулів та набуття навичок та вмій, які разом визначають поведінку людини стосовно його фізичних (тілесних) характеристик. Практично всім нам доводиться займатися фізичною культурою у своєму житті – займаючись спортом, активно відпочиваючи або відвідуючи заняття з фізкультури. Він ототожнюється з урахуванням фізичної підготовленості та здоров'я, прагненням до правильної постави тіла та правильного психофізичного розвитку. Фізична культура сильно пов'язана з мораллю, оскільки вона видима в усіх формах фізичної культури. Нині велику роль у шкільній освіті відіграє медична освіта, яка реалізується на окремих навчальних етапах. Завдяки цьому вже в школі ми можемо виробити звичку дбати систематично про власне здоров'я та приймати рішення про активну участь у фізичній культурі. Фізична підготовка вже мала велике значення для первісних людей, оскільки вони повинні були бути сильними, придатними, здоровими, стійкими до хвороб та мінливого клімату. Багато вчених цікавились спортом та фізичною культурою. Початки фізичного виховання в Європі слід віднести до Стародавньої Греції.

Ключові слова: професійний спорт, оздоровча освіта, фізична культура, мораль.

Introduction. Sociology as an independent scientific discipline developed in Poland at the end of the 19th century. Initially, it was almost exclusively the nature of analyzes and theoretical theorems, maintained on a relatively high floor of generality¹. As such, therefore, it had only relative separateness from social philosophy and, on the other hand, economics. The most exposed place, in terms of both quantity and quality, was taken by orientation, which considered macro-social problems in terms of historical materialism. Nevertheless, from the dawn of this orientation, very different search directions have appeared: from the creative attitude of continuation (Kazimierz Kelles Krauz 1872–1908, Ludwik Krzywicki 1858–1941), through evident economism and mechanism in the interpretation of social phenomena (Róża Luksemburg 1871–1919), to the concept of the dialectical opposition (Bolesław Limanowski 1835–1935, Edward Abramowski 1868–1918)². In the 20th century, this orientation initially developed towards, on the one hand, extensive historical and sociological studies and, on the other, empirical studies. The shape was largely influenced by the theoretical concepts of Max Weber (1864–1920) and Karol Mannheim (1867–1951). The naturalistic concept of Ludwik Gumpłowicz (1838–1909) was well-known on a global scale, but not having such a large range of influence. However, in the 1920s and 1930s, two schools that were very important for today's state of sociology in Poland were formed. The first, whose creator was Florian

Znanięcki (1882–1958), adopted the name of humanistic sociology. The basic theoretical and methodological assumption of this school was the thesis that social phenomena are not only objective but also subjective. In other words, it was about showing the social world as it is reflected in individual and social consciousness. This concept was associated with a specific selection of material in empirical research. First of all, personal documents, such as diaries, letters, etc. were used. The assumptions of this school found expression in all of Znanięcki's and his pupils' work, and in particular in the classic work published by that author together with William I. Thomas Polish peasant in Europe and America (1918) and the fourth volume work written by Józef Chałasiński (1904–1979): Young generation of peasants (1938). The second school owes its creation to Stefan Czarnowski (1879–1937), the author of numerous sociological works and the sociological and historical concept of culture. In his analyzes, he explicitly referred to the tradition of sociology of Emil Durkheim (1858–1917) and the tradition of historicism. The environment of Polish sociologists is dominated by the belief that sociology – like other social sciences – is not only to interpret and explain the social world, but also to create theoretical premises and formulate practical directives for its transformation. Hence, there are vivid interests in Poland of the axiological assumptions of sociology and the rules for transforming descriptive sentences about reality into normative theorems and directives of practical action. In addition, there is a belief in the equal importance of studying the

¹ Merton R., *Teoria socjologiczna i struktura społeczna*, PWN, Warszawa 2002, s. 56-58.

² Dziubiński Z., Krawczyk Z., *Socjologia kultury Fizycznej*, AWF, Warszawa 2011, s. 23-25.

past, present and future of the social world³. According to the principle of historicism and holistic view of reality, the categories of structure and social change are assumed as the main categories in sociological analyzes. Also important is the tendency to search for the subject of sociological research not only within the country, but also on a global, global scale. Hence, going beyond Polish issues to follow social processes in other societies, both developed and developing ones, e.g. processes taking place in Africa and Asia. Hence the traditional cooperation of Polish sociologists with sociologists from neighboring countries, but also Western Europe and America. This is manifested not only in the far-reaching substantive and organizational integration of activities in the International Sociological Association, participation in world congresses and sociological seminars, international sociological publications, but also in joint research undertaken with sociologists in many countries. In a word, sociology in Poland is open to both new social facts on a global scale and to new theoretical orientations. For years, macro-social approaches have been associated primarily with the holistic-dialectic tradition, but dialogue with other theoretical and methodological orientations is also lively. Important influences of these orientations on contemporary sociology in Poland are also visible. Among the most famous, which had a decisive impact on contemporary sociology in Poland, the following should be mentioned: functionalism (Bronisław Malinowski 1884–1942), systemic sociology (Talcott Parsons 1902–1978, Robert K. Merton 1910–2003), structuralism (Claude Levi-Strauss 1908), experience of cultural anthropology and symbolic interactionism. Neopositivist orientation in sociology also has a considerable number of supporters, however, it is probably the most criticized. Methodological assumptions and in practice assume the necessity of functioning of historical, theoretical, analytical and empirical sociology as complementary tendencies. Probably the greatest achievements have Polish sociology in the field of so-called specific sociology. The most developed,

rich in synthetic studies is the sociology of villages and cities. This is associated with the processes of industrialization and urbanization of the country, as well as with the wider processes of transforming agrarian society into urbanized. Other, already specific, fields of sociology are – on the one hand – sociology of organization, industry and work, and – on the other – sociology of culture. The latter, moreover, tends to divide further into: sociology of literature, sociolinguistics, sociology of art, theater, film, sport, etc.

Finally, sociology of health and medicine and – on the other hand – sociology of upbringing, youth, social pathology and resocialization have great achievements, both theoretical and practical. The traditional branches of sociology, such as the sociology of the dynamics of social structures (in particular of class and vocational structures) and the sociology of politics are also developing dynamically. The achievements of specific sociologies are the most important symptom of the development of Polish sociology in the last fifty years. Although progress is advised in the achievements of sociology in Poland, there is a fairly widespread belief in the sociological environment of its deficiencies. It is pointed out that the quantitative data collected by sociologists, as well as extensive theoretical analyzes – have not yet led to the emergence of a new, required and maturity, synthetic theory of modern society, two Polish, as well as on a global scale. In addition, the problems of the relationship between theory and empathy have not been sufficiently explained. The case is less drastic in the area of specific sociology. New and more numerous attempts at synthesis appear here, although they are still not completely satisfactory. As a rule, the so-called conceptual empiricism, i.e. that empirical research is to lead to the verification or falsification of theoretical hypotheses.

However, a large number of studies are also conducted in this area, whose authors describe the facts, conduct statistical analysis of data, without worrying about whether they can be theoretically explained and without making conscious theoretical assumptions. These difficulties arise even more on the upper floors of theoretical analysis. Generally speaking, there is

³ Dziubiński Z., Krawczyk Z., *Socjologia kultury Fizycznej*, AWF, Warszawa 2011, s. 101-104.

weak cooperation between micro- and macrosociology. Consequently, macro-sociology often offends axiology that is too detached from social reality, while micro-sociology collects empirical data that can hardly be synthesized. In this situation, the desire to create medium-range theory appears more and more often. It seems that Polish sociology in this respect shared the fate of world sociology, in which the deficiencies and even crisis of sociological theory are more and more often discussed.

The practical functions of sociology in Poland are implemented in two ways: «engineering through rationalization» and «engineering through manipulation». Let's explain the above wording. Firstly, we understand the concept of «engineering through rationalization» as creating scientific premises for the concept of social change implemented in practice. It occurs indisputably, but to an insufficient extent, mainly due to the weaknesses of the general sociological theory already discussed.

On the other hand, greater effects are obtained in the area of influencing the common consciousness of society, in popularizing sociological knowledge, in building the «sociological imagination» of broad social circles. In this regard, we note the undeniable impact of sociology, given the significant progress in the development of secondary and higher education and the development of mass education transmitted mainly by the mass media, where social knowledge is widely popularized. Speaking of «engineering through manipulation», we mean the impact of sociological empirical research and expertise on the functioning of the system of organizations and institutions in modern society. The practical significance of sociology in this regard is particularly large in countries with a pluralistic organization system and rapid transformation of economic, social and cultural life.

Almost all of us have to deal with physical culture in our lives – playing sports, actively relaxing or attending physical education classes. It is identified with attention to physical fitness and health, striving for the correct body posture, and proper psychophysical development.

We believe that physical culture is strongly associated with morality because it is visible in

all forms of physical culture. Nowadays, health education, which is implemented at individual educational stages, plays a big role in school education. Thanks to this, already at school we can develop the habit of caring systematically for our own health and decide on active participation in physical culture. Physical fitness was already of great importance to primitive people, because they had to be strong, fit, healthy, resistant to diseases and a changing climate. Many scholars were interested in sport and physical culture. The beginnings of physical education in Europe should be traced to ancient Greece.

Especially Athens, its junior high school and the educational system of children and youth, called kalokagatia, are to this day a model that provided the state with efficient and healthy citizens prepared for public, military and utilitarian activities⁴. From the dawn of antiquity, the model of an ideal pupil was considered. Emphasis was placed on physical education. In the sporting struggle, according to the idea of religion, victory was not a value in itself, but was given to the gods as a demonstration of strength, beauty, nobility and virtue⁵. In modern sport, we meet with the abandonment of the main moral principles and standards of work ethics: dignity, pure play, brotherhood, caring or hooligan behavior of fans, use of doping agents, and corruption. I think, however, that the modern development of civilization is not conducive to physical activity. Technological facilities, computerization, all inventions minimize physical activity in our everyday lives. From my own experience and observation, I can say that often when we remember our school period, we forget about the subject of physical education. Some of us took part in classes with enormous commitment, and the other part of the students tried by all means to avoid classes without realizing the importance of this subject. Exempting students from physical education lessons is often done

⁴ Urniaż J., Jurgielewicz-Urniaż M., *Rozwój szkolnego wychowania fizycznego na przestrzeni dziejów w Polsce a współczesny problem jego unikania*, Kultura fizyczna, 2015, nr 2., s. 15.

⁵ Leśniak-Moczuk A.D., *Historyczne i współczesne aspekty kultury w sporcie*, Młoda Humanistyka.com, 2017, nr 3., s. 1.

with the consent of the parents and it is not always due to the child's health. I think that the problem of dismissals mainly affects people who are less physically fit. Fear of ridicule, fear of getting a poor assessment or conviction of low attractiveness of classes are in my opinion the main reasons for the student's release from physical education classes. Physical education contributes not only to improving physical fitness, form or appearance but also shapes our approach to physical activity as well as implements it into a healthy way of spending free time. In my opinion, thanks to physical education, we know how to take care of our body's health.

Teaches us the right attitude to our body. According to A. Pawłucki, the sense of such activities is conducive to creating the common good, which should be understood as a good that man desires to improve himself and other participants of social life⁶. What determines our physical culture? In my opinion, the decisive influence is what tastes we have, how we live. Movement is an essential component of a healthy lifestyle that promotes the development of our body. Physical activity and sport are two forms of physical activity that are worth paying attention to. This has a huge impact on our development and growth during childhood. In adulthood, it allows us to maintain health and fitness. Regular and systematic activity causes that the aging process slows down. It also helps you deal with stress better. In order to better understand the meaning of the topic of work «Moral problems in modern physical culture and health education», I would like to clarify the concepts. Morality is about reflection on views about good behavior. It is treated as a phenomenon occurring in social relations.

When analyzing the concept of morality, it should be emphasized that it refers to various areas of reality: assessments, norms, experiences – e.g. remorse, deeds and attitudes, criteria, as well as patterns of behavior or cognitive authorities (moral sense, free will, moral sense). By definition, morality is «the overall behavior and attitudes of an individual or group, evaluat-

ed according to some socially functioning system of assessments and moral norms»⁷. It is very important that in our everyday life, physical culture is of fundamental importance, and at any age. According to Maciej Demel, «Physical culture includes all the values that are associated with the physical form and physical functioning of man, both in his own subjective sense, as well as in the socially objectified image. These values – generally speaking – efficiency, fitness, beauty. Similarly, to other cultural values, they have a dynamic character, shape human views and attitudes, so they are part of the worldview and customs»⁸.

In turn, Z. Krawczyk believes that physical culture is a relatively integrated and consolidated system of behaviors in the field of care for physical development, mobility, human health and beauty, running according to the patterns adopted in a given community, as well as the results of these behaviors⁹. As a characteristic feature of physical culture was recognized: the field of care for the body and physical functioning of man. When thinking about physical culture, a lot of people focus only on the physical functioning of man. It also includes such values as: personality, views and attitudes of the man who is its participant or recipient. The sense of physical culture concerns both the body and the spirit, mind and personality. Currently, the forms of participation in physical culture include:

- physical recreation,
- motor rehabilitation,
- sports.

The foundation of physical culture in each country is the school physical education system. I think that physical education plays the role of a message, which is focused on creating the right set of attitudes and attitudes, the transmission of messages associated with it, as well as hardening for environmental stimuli and acquiring skills and abilities that together determine the behavior of a person in relation to his physical (bodily) characters.

⁷ <https://sjp.pwn.pl/sjp/moralno%C5%9B%C4%87;2568434>

⁸ Forum dyskusyjne kierunku Turystyka i Rekreacja, Bartosz Łącki, 2008

⁹ Z. Krawczyk, *Socjologia kultury fizycznej*, AWF Warszawa, 1995 s.28

⁶ Pawłucki A., *Nauki o kulturze fizycznej*, Wrocław 2013, s. 28-29.

Piramida aktywności fizycznej

Fig. 1. <http://rogalikodkuchni.blogspot.com/2015/06/piramida-aktywnosci->

Health education is a process in which the people's habit of caring for their own health and that of others is formed.

Very often the topic in the school environment or health education is to be a separate subject. I think it's a good idea because young people would deepen their knowledge about health, their own body.

This would help shape attitudes related to hygiene, disease prevention and effective care. Health education is implemented by the school at individual educational stages, especially in physical education classes, but also on other subjects.

It is at school that the habit of systematically taking care of health is created. It should be present every day in the child's life and then throughout its entire period.

Often, however, we focus only on physical health and, according to the definition of the World Health Organization, health «is not only

a complete absence of illness or disability, but also a state of full physical, mental and social well-being»¹⁰.

We think that by putting emphasis on improving our physical condition, playing various sports, we make us forget about the spiritual and mental sphere.

A person is a bodily and spiritual entity that functions not only in the sphere of biology, matter, but also the spiritual world.

This unity means that everything that is spiritual has its relation to the physical sphere and vice versa¹¹.

¹⁰ WHO 1948

¹¹ Barth G. (2011) *Osoba a edukacja. Kilka uwag z perspektywy hermeneutyki personalistycznej*. Kultura i Wychowanie, nr 2(2), s. 75-83.

Fig.2. <http://www.zakazny.pl/edukacja-zdrowotna>

If our brain is in good condition, our whole body is functioning properly.

In order for people to make changes in their lifestyle, they must have appropriate knowledge about health education that they obtain in the education process.

Among the objectives of health education, particularly relevant from the point of view of health promotion, are the following:

- Making people aware that they make decisions and make choices about their health and lifestyle, and thus are responsible for their own health and affect other people's health,
- Impact on policy makers from various public sectors to be aware of their role in creating conditions that support social, economic and organizational changes that will improve people's health¹².

Morality in the aspect of physical education applies not only to sport and its benefits.

It also plays a very important role in health education, which in the core curriculum is considered a separate department of physical education.

Ensuring that our eating habits are correct, promoting a healthy lifestyle by teaching that smoking or the use of stimulants are harmful, and strengthening knowledge that sleep length and quality also has a positive effect on our well-being.

According to the current core curriculum of early childhood education in physical education, a third-grade student in health education:

- cares for personal hygiene and cleanliness of clothing,
- they know the importance of proper nutrition and physical activity for health,
- they know that they cannot take their own medicines or use chemicals contrary to their intended use,
- ensures correct posture, e.g. sitting at a bench, at a table,
- observes the rules of safe behavior during physical activities, uses sports equipment in accordance with their intended purpose,
- can choose a safe place for games and motion games, knows who to turn to for help in the event of a threat to health or life¹³.

A person who is completely healthy adapts to the changing environment and develops in all aspects of life.

Balance, harmony and full physical, mental and social capabilities as well as optimal use of development potential are also important aspects of health.

We call this approach a holistic health model. It assumes that human health consists of several interrelated dimensions or resources that can be consciously discovered and used¹⁴.

¹² Woynarowska B., *Organizacja I Realizacja Edukacji Zdrowotnej W Szkole*, ORE, Warszawa 2014.

¹³ Podstawa programowa z komentarzami Tom 8.

¹⁴ W. Ostreża, M. Plichcińska, A. Rogacka, B. Wolny, P. Wróblewski, *Wychowanie fizyczne i edukacja zdrowotna w bezpiecznej i przyjaznej szkole*, ORE, Warszawa 2015, s. 6.

Fig. 3. W. Ostręga, M. Plichcińska, A. Rogacka, B. Wolny, P. Wróblewski, *Wychowanie fizyczne i edukacja zdrowotna w bezpiecznej i przyjaznej szkole*, ORE, Warszawa 2015, s. 6.

Each of these dimensions has a major impact on our health. Already in the youngest school classes attention is paid to behaviors that affect our physical and psychosocial health. Physical activity helps us reduce stress, increases our self-esteem, fights depression and makes us cope better in difficult and uncomfortable situations. Already in the youngest children, the spiritual dimension allows developing empathy for peers, but also for the elderly. The ability to behave during defeats or victories is a very important issue. The youngest participants find it very difficult to accept defeat and understand it, which leads to negative behavior. There is more and more physical violence and aggression in schools. Often victims are weaker and worse people from physical education. They are easy sights for children who cope with physical activity very well. In my opinion, the reason is the lack of spending free time outdoors. In my opinion, the reason is the lack of spending free time outdoors. Children cannot discharge their energy because they spend most of their time in front of a computer, x-box or telephone. It used to be that a child used his free time to play and spend time with his peers. Mainly physical education teachers have an impact on all aspects of health education, but not only they should be burdened with this burden. Also, parents and guardians should be responsible for implementing correct behaviors that strive to engage in physical activity and to encourage others to a healthy lifestyle. I believe that these youngest

minds should be taught to be role models. Fluency and ambiguity in understanding physical culture is a consequence of many circumstances. Definitely problems with definitions with culture in general come to the fore, but also too diverse content hidden in the term «physical». In addition, this category, before it found the right of citizenship in science, had previously functioned in the common consciousness, which was an attempt to rationalize specific practical activities, especially in the field of education of the young generation. In this way, she was entangled in certain connotations, with difficulty succumbing to unambiguous determination. However, even in order to avoid fundamental misunderstandings resulting from the different semantic range of the category we are interested in, let us try to isolate the basic approaches to physical culture as a specific field of culture. It seems that they can be reduced to four relatively separate types.

Physical culture is the whole of the material environment shaped by man in accordance with his needs, possibilities and values. Thanks to this, it has a specific human dimension and as such does not exist outside the human world. Quite the opposite – it is an integral part of it and forms the basis of all culture. This definition of physical culture includes both the world of «humanized nature» and so-called material culture, i.e. the «artificial» human environment that has a negative effect on his way of life. In this collection of designations, man will finally find himself as a

physical being connected with countless threads to the entire natural environment and co-existing with him on the principle of relative homeostasis.

Physical culture is a system of values, activities and their effects in the field of human physical activity defined by external conditions and stimulated by social needs. This will include both physical work and any other behavior aimed at improving the human species, health, fitness and body expression.

The forms and content of these activities are relative and depend on the type of society, the degree of its development and the system of meanings and symbols. They are therefore socially determined and have social functions.

Physical culture is all forms of human physical activity undertaken consciously and intentionally to multiply the health, development, physical fitness and beauty of a person, subordinated to the model of a comprehensive, harmonious and dynamic personality. In this sense, the creation and recreation of the body is complementary to other socialization and educational effects on the individual. These forms tend to institutionalize and are currently manifested primarily in the form of games and activities, gymnastics, various sports and tourism. This understanding of physical – or otherwise – bodily culture, lay at the root of the pedagogical and educational currents that have now developed in countries under the dominant influence of European civilization.

Physical culture understood as a synonym of sport. Both in Poland and other Central and Eastern European countries, this understanding of the category we are interested in occurs only sporadically. Quite the opposite, we meet here very often (Matwiejew 1984) an attempt to contrast these two concepts. There is talk of physical culture and sport as disjunctive areas. However, this separation has not yet been sufficiently substantiated theoretically, and therefore there is often reasoned negation. On the other hand, the identification of physical culture and sport is usually found in Western literature, in which the first concept is expressed by means of another term, namely «physical activity». However, specialists are more and more consistently using the concept of «sport» and derivative terms: sports science, sport philosophy, sport sociology, sport pedagogy, sport psychology, etc. In the field of physical culture sciences, this tendency is also evident in the field of natural sciences; for example, anthropology,

physiology or biomechanics of sport are mentioned here. The four basic types of understanding of physical culture that have been reconstructed above have analytical and ordering significance. Our intention is not to value them, and even more so hierarchy from the point of view of the degree of correctness or usefulness. They were formulated according to the axiologically neutral principle of the semantic scope of this category. The first understanding of physical culture we distinguished is global, therefore it can be a convenient bridge for the integration of the discussed field with the sciences of man, culture and nature, and above all with the axiological sciences. The second and third understandings are similar in scope, although they do not overlap completely. The second also includes directly utilitarian activities, namely physical work, in addition, it is more useful for basic (theoretical) sciences of physical culture. On the other hand, the specified third type of understanding of the field we are interested in has been taken from the institutional and practical side, which is why it was appropriated primarily by practical sciences. Referring to these two approaches, we adopt the following definition of the field that occupies us: Physical culture is a relatively integrated and consolidated system of behavior in the field of care for physical development, mobility, health, beauty, bodily perfection and human expression, following the patterns adopted in a given community, and the results of these behaviors. The mosaic of theoretical and methodological orientations typical of contemporary sociology of physical culture is extremely difficult to systematize, and even less so classification or even typology. This state of affairs consists of at least several circumstances. First, the authors of most of the empirical research conducted in the subject of interest do not formulate their own theories explicitly; they do not always associate their search with a specific sociological theory (Heinemann 1990: 10-11). They most often refer to general categories and sociological concepts and in their perspective consider selected problems specific to physical culture as a social phenomenon. Hence, even synthetic works, including academic textbooks, moreover, most often multi-author, rarely in their concept and thematic structure are subordinated to a specific, sociological theory. In addition, the very concept of theory, including sociological theory, functions – as is known – in many meanings, and the attempt to

reduce them to a «common denominator» results in definitions that are general enough to be difficult to use in the analysis of various texts that can be included in issues of physical culture sociology. For example, one of the experts in world sociological theory, Francis M. Abraham, says that by theory he will understand «a conceptual scheme useful for explaining observed regularities or relationships between two or more variables» (Abraham 1982: 3). And Robert K. Merton notes that sociological theory can be understood as:

- 1) methodology,
- 2) general sociological orientations,
- 3) analysis of sociological concepts,
- 4) post factum sociological interpretations,
- 5) empirical generalizations in sociology,
- 6) sociological theory in the general sense.

Therefore, without going into more detailed considerations on this complicated subject, we will assume after Piotr Sztompka that «all sociological theory is any set of ontological, epistemological and methodological assumptions, abstract concepts and general assertions about social reality, intended to provide an explanation of available descriptive knowledge about it, and guide further research».

Searching for the theoretical implications of the effects of sociological studies and research in the field that interests us, this can be done in two ways:

- 1) either by starting from the known theoretical and methodological directions appropriate to contemporary sociology, try to observe whether among hundreds of printed publications and articles devoted to the field we occupy there will be ones that without much hesitation can be included in any of them,

- 2) be, while reviewing and critically analyzing the more «theoretically ambitious» works of sociologists of physical culture, try to posteriori try to construct theoretical and methodological approaches specific to specific authors' collections. Using this first approach, let's try to make a typology of theoretical and methodological orientations characteristic of authors dealing with the relationship between physical culture and society.

HEALTH EDUCATION AND SUPPLEMENTATION

In the modern world, we are increasingly reaching for products that complement our daily diet. The problem concerns the use of supple-

ments and boosters that help faster fat burning and building muscle mass. Currently, according to the IOC Medical Committee, caffeine, creatine and sodium bicarbonate are among the scientifically proven supplements. Carnitine, vitamins, BCAA, MCT, HMB, microelements, plant extracts and other antioxidant substances have been classified as those with scientifically unconfirmed and limited effectiveness. They support physical performance, stimulate energy production and mass development. There is a growing conviction among athletes about the need to support exercise capacity. The conducted research shows that the vast majority of athletes (86.5 %), including 91 % women and 82 % men, declared taking nutritional supportive measures¹⁵.

These people expect the effects of their effort in the form of greater physical performance or better sports results, and in my opinion, to achieve this goal, regular and systematic physical training is enough. These drugs have a detrimental effect on health, can ruin athletic performance and training effects. However, not only athletes reach for supplements. They are very often and willingly used by beginners, who play sports in an amateur way. Therefore, I believe that in the earliest years of education we should be provided with knowledge about the use of various supplements – the desired and the undesirable. However, I am aware that it should appear in a different form at every stage of education. It is becoming increasingly common for children to choose what meal to eat by buying it at the school store. Parents, not preparing a meal for their children, trust that the children will spend their money on breakfast well. However, most children give in to temptation and buy unhealthy products in nearby supermarkets or neighborhood stores. A more serious problem is that young people who start their sports journey, wanting to impress others, decide to consume substances of different origin. They reach for illegal supplements, which often ends in tragedy. The current official definition of doping is «the violation of one or more of the anti-doping rules set out in Articles 2.1–2.8 of the World Anti-Doping Code»¹⁶. Over the years, the definition of doping has changed many times, but the meaning has

¹⁵ Jegier A., *Dozwolone i niedozwolone wspomaganie zdolności wysiłkowych człowieka*, PTMS, Łódź 2007.

¹⁶ <http://www.doping-prevention.com/pl/doping-w-sensieogolnym/definicja-dopingu.html>

remained the same. Sports doping improves the athlete's performance in an unnatural way. Each player is responsible for his actions and what he takes. Consuming such products may lead to the wasted sports career. Even in the history of Polish sport you can find doping scandals. Polish weightlifter, Zbigniew Kaczmarek, two-time world and European champion, three-time Olympian won the gold medal at the Montreal Games. He was by far the best, but he did not enjoy his success for too long. After carrying out anti-doping tests, he

was found banned as a result of which, after three months, he was removed from the Olympic medal. Kaczmarek still tried chances during the Moscow Games, but it did not bring any success. Another example is the Polish weightlifter, Tomasz Zieliński, who had to leave the village during the Olympics in Rio de Janeiro. He was found to have elevated levels of the banned substance – nandrolone. The weightlifter was immediately suspended as a competitor.

Fig. 5. <https://sport.tvp.pl/24341183/najwieksze-skandale-dopingowe-w-historii-sportu>

Fig.6. <http://dziennikzwiazkowy.com/sport/rio-tomasz-zielinski-przylapany-na-dopingu/>

NUTRIERS AND OTHER DRUGS AND HEALTH EDUCATION

Among young people, a very serious problem that still needs to be solved is the popularity of using such drugs as smoking, drinking alcohol or taking legal highs. In the 21st century, we can observe an increase in youth interest in this phenomenon. However, I noticed that more and more programs are being created to raise awareness of the importance of protecting our health. Thanks to these programs, we learn to skillfully make decisions in difficult situations and how to deal with stress. Smoking is a current and serious problem that schools are facing. Virtually at every stage of education we can observe stu-

dents smoking tobacco. The percentage of adolescents who smoke daily increases systematically during puberty from 6 % through about 16 % at the age of 15 to about 25 % at the age of 18¹⁷. Another huge threat are the so-called afterburners. They have been around for many years, the only thing that changes is the forms, chemical compositions and the possibility of obtaining them. Despite very widespread actions that inform about the harmful effects of using these dangerous drugs, young people and

¹⁷ Ponczek D., Olszowy I., *Ocena stylu życia młodzieży i świadomości jego wpływu na zdrowie*, Hygeia Public Health 2012, 47(2): 174–182.

sometimes athletes reach for them. People who take these substances try to escape problems in this way. They don't even realize they're addicted. The effects can be tragic and many young athletes have lost their careers through drugs and alcohol. However, taking care of your fu-

ture is not everything. We have only one health, we should take care of it. I think everyone is aware of this. Without health, we are not able to achieve our goals and develop our skills. It is important to see addicts (at school, family, work) to help them as soon as possible.

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